

Travails of an Aging Society on a Country's Economic Health

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Abstract

Human Civilization has evolved to deal with risk, the risk posed by uncertainties and the risk of financial struggle at old age. In early times, before the introduction of pension systems, “the family has been the traditional social institution for the care of the elderly, who generally lived and worked with their children”. (Knodel, Chayovan and Siriboon; 1992). Even until recently, greater than 50% of the world's old people are estimated to rely on informal and traditional arrangements for income security, as per reported by the World Bank (1994). However, falling fertility, rising cost of living, increasing number of nuclear families means that the elderly in most countries cannot expect to completely rely on their children. Traditional old age support mechanisms are gradually collapsing particularly because of the third phase of the demographic transition; Demographic-Burden phase. The fact that people are living longer, with better access and improvement in healthcare, may render the current social systems in many countries, unsustainable.

This paper gives an in-depth analysis of the economic impacts of the demographic transition, why current pension systems in many countries will render inadequate in the coming years and why India needs a young population to stay ahead of other countries. An aging population affects economies in multiple areas. Firstly, a fall in labour force participation reduces the growth of GDP, working-age people pay more to support the elderly, and public budgets strain under the burden of the higher total cost of health and retirement programs for old people. Another aspect of ageing societies is the ‘Crowding-Out’ effect, people tend to be more conservative in their investment and saving practices. The consumption pattern significantly changes and people only spend on more essential items along with a rise in their healthcare costs. An aging population has less labour to satisfy the demands of the country, there is a labour crunch which may lead to more imports from other countries further affecting their currency and purchasing power. Public sector transfers for pensions, health care, and long-term care are a particular problem as populations age, because these payments, even after subtracting the portion funded by tax payments from the elderly, absorb a large portion of public budgets. Projections indicate that typically these programs will be unsustainable unless taxes are raised or benefits reduced or both.

Key Words-Demographic Transition, Aging Population, Retirement Income System

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Introduction

Aging is a natural, irreversible process with its own challenges and opportunities. Globally people worldwide are living longer than before. With advances in medical science, most people can expect to live into their sixties and beyond. Almost every country in the world is experiencing growth in both the size and the proportion of older persons in the population. Social historian **Philippe Aries** (1962) pointed out that someone's age in medieval society was not based on chronological years, but on factors such as their strength, abilities, and appearance. This was because there was a lack of official documentation to keep track of one's age.

Data has shown that, 1 in 6 people in the world will be aged 60 years or over by 2030. At this time the share of the population aged 60 years and over will increase from 1 billion in 2020 to 1.4 billion. By 2050, the world's population of people aged 60 years and older will double (2.1 billion). 426 million will be the expected population of persons aged 80 years or older between 2020 and 2050. It's shocking to see that in Japan 30% of the population is already over 60 years old.

The shift in distribution of a country's population towards older ages started in high-income countries, it is now low- and middle-income countries that are experiencing the greatest change. This change is called- *Population ageing*. The data shows that approximately three decades from now, two-thirds of the world's population over 60 years will live in low- and middle-income countries

For the first time in history, there are more elderly people in the world than young children, (United Nations, 2018; BBC, 2018). Estimates show that the number of people over 65 years have outnumbered the number of people under 5 years by the end of 2018. A similar current trend, points to the fact that there is a growing disparity between the number of old and young people across the globe. According to the BBC, "this widening gap symbolises a trend that demographers have been tracking for decades"; in most countries, we are all living longer

and not having enough children to support the population. This is contrary to the belief that increasing population is a threat to our survival.

Some of the effects of an older population on the economy are as follows:

- The country's workforce will be predominantly older, and the productivity of economies will be dependent on this.
- The workforce will need to be better trained in technology and barriers to work will have to be removed.
- A system wherein education and training are provided at regular intervals, as opposed to just initially, will have to be adopted.
- Workers will require more flexibility in their day-to-day responsibilities.
- Older people, who may be unable to travel every day to work.

Background

In this paper, we shall discuss about this demographic transition, and how it will impact our economies in the future. There is consensus that governments need to act in order to defuse this “*ageing time-bomb*” and they have been trying to do so. Recently China reviewed and amended its infamous “one-child policy” and introduced the “three-child policy” with sops to encourage child birth.

Population in the pre-industrial era grew slow for the most of human history, the growth rate was somewhere around 0.1%. Sharp changes in the world population growth rate were seen in the last 200 years.

To understand the world population growth rate we need to know the working of it.

- Working-age population = The number of persons in the age group of 15 to 64 years.
- Labour force = The sum of employed and unemployed workers in the economy.

- Labour force participation rate (LFPR) = The percentage of the working-age population that is in the labour force
- $LFPR = \text{Labour force} \times 100 \% / \text{working-age population}$

According to Lee (2003, p.167), this transition began “around 1800 with declining mortality in Europe”. This demographic transition has now spread to all parts of the world and is projected to be completed by 2100. Before the demographic transition, people had a short life expectancy, high fertility rates and the population was relatively young. During the transition, “first mortality declines, causing population growth first to accelerate and then slow”. After the transition, people live long lives, fertility rate among women is low and the population is relatively old.

Today, two thirds of the world’s older persons live in the developing regions, where their numbers are growing faster than in the developed regions. (WPA, UN, 2017) ^{iv}. Some countries where this is seen are - China, India and a few South-Asian and African countries.

A sample was taken from 20 families residing in the neighbourhood area in a metropolitan city in India. The family history was taken telephonically from the eldest living member of the family. Out of the 20 families 90% of the families shared that they had more than 8-10 living children during 1930-50. The remaining 10% of the families i.e. two families shared that their great grandfather had 12 children from a single wife.

“Having lived in India for a major part of my life, I have had first-hand experience of witnessing the fall in fertility rates among my family. My grandmother (now aged 80 years) had 10 siblings however she had only 2 children herself”.

Presently, majority of the population in India is in the ‘working-age’ (67%; between 15 to 64 years). The fertility rate in India has halved since the 1980’s and is showing a downward decline trend. If this continues, India could also face a severe challenge with ageing

population in 30 years' time, i.e. around 2050. As the population structure is changing, today we have a population that is rapidly ageing in India, although the effects of that are not seen currently, but will be seen in the coming years.

Figure A(above) highlights the striking increase in old age population of India.

Figure B(above) shows a comparison of population structure of India between 1950 and 2050.

Parts of the world including Europe, UK, Japan, etc. have a shrinking working-age population. Research has indicated that the Land of rising sun-Japan, is also home to more than 80,000 centenarians. By 2036, people aged 65 and over will represent a third of the population. Since 2011, the Japanese population has also been shrinking: it is a rare case of large country whose overall population is becoming smaller in prosperous and peaceful times (Think Tank- European Parliament). If the trend continues, it could weaken the country's role on the world stage, and this could have serious implications for the U.S., and the future of Asia. Besides the trends foreseen, Japan is facing problems such as, shifting disease burden, increased expenditure on health and long-term care, labour-force shortages, dissaving, and potential problems with old-age income security.

Figure C

(Source: researchgate.net)

Figure C(above) indicates a population pyramid comparison of Japan in 1950 and in 2020. The result indicated in the comparative population is very alarming highlighting rapid aging. It is only a matter of time till most countries face a similar concern. Aging population has severe implications on the economy of a country. A dwindling labour force will further compress our already narrow tax base. At the same time, an ageing population will lead to increased public spending on health-care and elderly services. Some commentators

conjecture that it further led to less vibrant economy, lower economic growth (measured by GDP) and lower living standard (measured by GDP per person).

This following map shows the change in age-dependency ratio from 1966 to 2020.

- Dependency ratio (total DR or overall DR or demographic DR) = the number of persons aged under 15 and those aged 65 and over per 1000 persons aged between 15 and 64.

$$DR = \frac{\#(x < 15) + \#(x \geq 65)}{\#(15 \leq x < 65)} \times 1000$$

Figure D(above) shows changes in Age Dependency Ratio from 1966 to 2020

An aging population affects economies in multiple areas which has a whirlpool effect in the following ways

- A fall in labour force participation reduces the growth of GDP, working-aged people pay more to support the elderly, and public budgets strain under the burden of the higher total cost of health and retirement programs for old people.
- The Crowding Out effect, in this the people tend to be more conservative in their investment and saving practices. The consumption pattern significantly changes, and people only spend on more essential items along with rise in their healthcare costs. An

ageing population has less Labour to satisfy the demands of the country, there is a Labour crunch (shortage) which may lead to more imports from other countries further affecting their currency and purchasing power.

- Public sector transfers for pensions, health care, and long-term care are a particular problem as populations age, because these payments, even after subtracting the portion funded by tax payments from the elderly, absorb a large portion of public budgets.
- Projections indicate that typically these programs will be unsustainable unless taxes are raised, or benefits reduced or both. The government's budget shrinks, because the tax base decreases, while the expenditure on dependencies increases for the whole society.
- Economic growth slows down as the aggregate labour supply decreases on one hand, and the aggregate saving decreases on the other. This means economic growth will slow down and reach an inflexion point if we do not respond appropriately.

Conclusion

With the introduction of technologies that reduce labour dependence and act as substitutes of manpower can change the course of history. Today, technologies such as Artificially Intelligent Robots, process automation already exist to replace people in the workplace.

India has a great challenge ahead regarding its population structure. There will be over 319 million people aged over 65 by 2050, threefold the number identified by the Census in 2011, according to the Longitudinal Ageing Study of India (LASI).

To lighten the impact of aging population, policies can be set up in place to mitigate the adverse consequences of low fertility. Those can include direct financial incentive such as tax deductions and allowances, child-care support, compatibility of work and family life. Some

other policies can include governmental support for infertility treatment and immigration to boost labour supply.

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